

Ash and wood fibres for sustainable and lightweight concrete

Various stabilization techniques are used for recovered wood-based side streams in groundworks/foundations. Granulated ash processed to coarse-grained material from side streams of power plants replace the filling and filter layer of natural aggregate in road and field structures. Processed ash in aggregates replace cement as binders. The ash may come from bark, saw dust, and various types of wood chips. Natural aggregate in concrete can be replaced with discarded, clean recycled wood fiber by 20-50% of the product volume.

Regional coverage and transferability

District heating and power plants as well as small combustion plants using wood-based fuels generate significant amounts of ash as by-product as it is the case today in Finland. Ash from wood-based biomass is potentially applicable for many purposes, e.g. for infrastructure groundwork. Transferability is demonstrated in many European regions.

Photo: Ecolan Oy/Yara, Finland

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Waste from incineration is recycled and re-used.
- ▶ The collection of waste from industrial sites as a raw material source for new products is upcycling.
- ▶ It replaces the layer of virgin sand used as frost insulation in road construction and infrastructure groundwork.
- ▶ Compared to conventional materials, products made of these materials are stronger, lighter and more ecological – environmental friendly.
- ▶ Recovering and stabilising waste materials is a smart, innovative technology.
- ▶ Recycling and reuse promotes the circular economy concept. New fibres from recycled wood can be processed to replace natural earth materials and cement, e.g., in paving and yard stones, and as a high performing material for noise barriers.